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पेटेंट कार्यालय का एक प्रकाशन
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(54) Title of the invention : JUTE FIBER MAT REINFORCED EPOXY BASED POLYMER COMPOSITES AND NANOCOMPOSITES

<p>(51) International classification :B29C0070080000, G01N0003080000, B29C0070300000, C08K0003040000, C08J0005060000</p> <p>(86) International Application No :NA Filing Date :NA</p> <p>(87) International Publication No : NA</p> <p>(61) Patent of Addition to Application Number :NA Filing Date :NA</p> <p>(62) Divisional to Application Number :NA Filing Date :NA</p>	<p>(71)Name of Applicant : 1)ARUN KUMAR SHARMA Address of Applicant :B-1219,B-block sagartaal road,near sagartaal chauraha Anand nagar,bahodapur gwalior -----</p> <p>Name of Applicant : NA Address of Applicant : NA</p> <p>(72)Name of Inventor : 1)Arun Kumar sharma Address of Applicant :b 1219 B block anand nagar bahodapur gwalior madhya pradesh India 474012 Gwalior -----</p> <p>2)Dr. rakesh Bhandari Address of Applicant :187, Vakil Colony,Bhilwara, 311001 Bhilwara -----</p> <p>3)Dr. Shri Krishna Dhakad Address of Applicant :B-6, Block-A ,UIT RGPV,Shivpuri ,473793 Shivpuri -----</p> <p>4)Sarika sharma Address of Applicant :b 1219 B block anand nagar bahodapur gwalior madhya pradesh India 474012 Gwalior -----</p> <p>5)Dr. Camelia Pinca – Bretotean Address of Applicant :Ap.16, Bl.3 ,nr.7, Str. Republicii,Hunedoara 331032 -----</p>
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(57) Abstract :

The purpose of this research is to evaluate the mechanical characteristics of a jute fiber/Multi wall Carbon Nanotube (MWCNT)/Graphene reinforced epoxy composite. This research examines the tensile characteristics of jute composites and study was completed using UTM. When the epoxy matrix is reinforced its mechanical, qualities improved. In comparison to artificial fibers, jute fiber offers better qualities throughout the composite sector. As part of this research, composites have been manufactured using hand layup procedure. Jute fibers accounted for a volume proportion of 30% in all instances and (Graphene+MWCNT) is in varying proportions. Experimental data were compared to determine the tensile properties of the composites that had been created. It has been shown that the qualities of all the created composites are highly influenced by the reinforcing material’s tensile characteristics.

Figure :1

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